

E-retrofitting can accelerate Europe's bus fleet electrification by 15 years

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Abstract

Minimizing climate risks will require accelerating the energy transition on all levels and in all sectors. Replacing 1.4 billion fossil with electric road vehicles will, however, be a process spanning multiple decades. Expanding electric bus transit has the potential to reduce the demand for electric cars while needing little additional infrastructure. Yet, accelerating the electrification of public mobility is a challenge in itself. This paper explores the system-wide effect of applying the emerging strategy of e-retrofitting to Europe's bus fleet. Diesel buses are thereby retrofitted with electric drive-trains, which reduces environmental impacts compared to the production of a new battery-electric bus. This strategy allows to accelerate bus fleet electrification by 15 years and to increase annual transport services by a maximum of 25%, all without the need to prematurely retire functioning buses. Applied across Europe, e-retrofitting buses can save up to 300 million tons of greenhouse gas emissions, generate jobs, offer business opportunities, reduce raw material demand, and requires minimal additional infrastructure.

Keywords

mobility transition | bus | climate change | public transport | electrification

1 Introduction

2 Stabilizing the climate necessitates to accelerate the phase out of fossil fuels [1–5]. Mobility has been
3 called a “roadblock” to climate mitigation [6], mainly because of its staggering dependence on fossil fuels.
4 Simultaneously, access to affordable and inclusive mobility is a basic need for everyone [7] and should be
5 provided with minimal impacts on planetary boundaries [8]. For all road vehicle types—from private cars
6 to long-distance trucks—mature battery electric options (battery electric vehicles - BEV) are available on
7 the market, which are consistently found as most environmentally friendly [9–11]. Yet, their share in new
8 registrations is still small [12, 13]. Replacing all 1.4 billion road vehicles globally [14]—almost all of them
9 are fossil powered—with new electric vehicles will take a long time, require large amounts of materials, and
10 be very costly [15]. A faster adoption of BEV would not only require increasing BEV share in new vehicle
11 sales, but also shorten the lifetime of existing fossil vehicles [15]. Though environmentally preferable [16],
12 scraping functioning vehicles is perceived as a waste of resources and counter to the narrative of a circular

13 economy [17]. Accelerating mitigation in mobility will therefore require strategies different from simple
14 replacements.

15 Emissions during driving are generated mainly by the fossil engine; the vehicle could drive emission-free,
16 if the fossil engine is replaced by an electric drive-train. Such a retrofitting strategy is pioneered across
17 vehicle types (e. g., buses [18], motorcycles [19], trains [20], trucks [21], mining trucks [22], ships [23] and
18 passenger cars [24, 25]) by a growing number of companies and start-ups (see Supplementary Materials
19 (SM) Section S2 for examples). This strategy leaves the vehicle structure intact and only replaces the
20 drive-train [26], maintaining the functional integrity of the vehicle and preserving parts of its material and
21 economic value. It only adds what is minimally necessary to defossilize operations and generates minimal
22 waste. Yet, batteries and electric motors, which are the main contributors of environmental impacts to
23 any BEV [11], are still necessary and a full electrification strategy would require fast scaling of battery
24 materials' supply chains, many of which are considered critical [27, 28]. Reducing the amount of batteries
25 required for mobility will need a shift towards more shared and public mobility. Today, more than $\frac{2}{3}$ of
26 all passenger kilometers in the EU are traveled by car and only 15% by rail and bus [29]. Land-based
27 public transport options are more efficient per transport distance than private car use [11, 30], which
28 is why a mode shift towards bus and rail has the potential to downscale mobility impacts during and
29 after the transition. Expanding rail is a comparatively slow and material-intensive strategy where rail
30 infrastructure has to be built [31]. In contrast, bus transport can be increased more rapidly, because the
31 required infrastructure (i. e., roads) already exists and becomes less frequented when private car use is
32 reduced. Dedicating more road space to buses and cycling makes bus transit more attractive [32] and
33 cycling safer [33].

34 Yet, less than 3% of all buses on European roads were fully electric (battery electric vehicles (BEV)
35 or trolley buses) in 2023 [34]. Replacing all remaining buses with new electric ones to meet cities' and
36 countries' emission targets will take time and requires investments, which are then missing for expanding
37 the bus fleet. And without expanding public transport services, it will be even harder to make reducing
38 private car use attractive.

39 In 2024, 80% of new bus sales were still diesel, gas, or hybrid [13]. And even if all new bus registrations
40 would be electric from now on, it would still take more than two decades to replace the entire fleet. Scraping
41 running diesel buses early would increase the investments necessary by public mobility operators and
42 require a significant up-scaling in BEV bus production. Applying the retrofit strategy to the existing diesel
43 bus fleet is an alternative, circular strategy, potentially capable of significantly accelerating electrification at
44 lower costs as well as energy and material demand. Currently, retrofitting companies are still niche players,
45 as retrofitting in small numbers requires extensive engineering on a case-by-case basis and individual
46 certifications. Additionally, the systemic effects on fleet electrification dynamics are so far under-explored
47 and policy support is lacking.

48 This paper shows that retrofitting existing diesel buses with battery electric drive-trains can significantly
49 contribute to accelerating the defossilization of mobility on a systemic level. Based on a growing number
50 of examples of e-retrofits on various vehicle types, a combined techno-economic, life cycle assessment and
51 system dynamics approach is used to quantify the system-wide effect of introducing retrofitting as a key
52 strategy to defossilizing Europe's bus fleet. The analysis focuses on Europe (EU+4), but the approach is
53 transferable to other contexts.

54 2 Method

55 A dynamic bus fleet model¹ for the European Union, Switzerland, Norway, United Kingdom, and Iceland
56 (EU+4) is build in the system dynamics tool Insightmaker [35]. The bus stock for EU+4 is split for
57 "diesel", "retrofit" and "BEV" sub-stocks. All other drive-trains are subsumed under "diesel", because
58 most of them are powered by gas or are hybrid, which have to be replaced as well [36]. Trolleybuses are
59 neglected because of their small share.

60 The diesel bus stock is further split in old and new diesel buses. Old buses are the initial stock in the
61 year 2000 and this stock is not replenished. All new diesel bus registrations from 2000 onward go into the
62 new diesel bus stock and retire according to their lifetime distribution. The retirement from the old diesel
63 bus stock can be calculated by subtracting the retirement of new diesel buses, which is determined by the
64 lifetime distribution, from total retirements between 2000 and 2024 derived from the overall stock and

¹The model can be accessed here: <https://www.insightmaker.com/insight/5ZnYCxNNIOhdSgbF6suugT/Bus-e-retrofit-release1>

65 flow balance in historic data [13] (see Section S3 in SM). In 2024, almost no old diesel bus is left in the
66 stock, with the remaining leaving this stock modeled as a first order decay function.

67 New diesel buses can be considered for retrofit after a specified year of registration. A fraction of all
68 buses produced after this year is therefore entering a separate sub-stock "Diesel for retrofit", which are
69 earmarked for retrofit. A 0.5% per year failure rate applied to this stock diminishes those buses which
70 may not become available for retrofit due to accidents or other failures. The remaining stock will be
71 progressively retrofitted after the retrofit start year and a maximum retrofit rate can be defined.

72 New BEV registrations follow the historic data from 2018 to 2024. Afterwards, the BEV share of all
73 new registrations is increased in a S-shaped curve to reach 100% in the year when diesel bus sales end.

74 The total number of buses can be adjusted in the scenarios after 2024 either through specifying a target
75 for new registrations or for total stock. Passenger transport performance can be calculated from the bus
76 stock, occupation, and annual driving distance. Emissions are calculated by multiplying both production
77 and operation in the different bus categories with emission intensity factors from life cycle assessments
78 [11] (see also Section S4 in SM) and, where electricity is used, by following the temporal development of
79 emission intensity of European electricity mix and the respective electricity demand. Similarly, total costs
80 are calculated by applying costs factors [37] to bus production and operation.

81 3 E-retrofitting strategies and environmental benefits

82 For e-retrofitting buses, the engine, gear box, transmission, fuel tank, and exhaust system need to
83 be removed and the containing materials (mostly steel and aluminum) become available for recycling,
84 increasing secondary raw material availability and reducing environmental impacts of material supply
85 [38]. A new electric motor, battery pack, and power electronics have to be fitted [18, 39]. Operationally,
86 the simplest way to do this is by replacing the rear axle of the bus with electric motors, reduction gear
87 boxes, motor controller, suspension, and brake systems pre-installed. Alternatively, the electric motor can
88 also be installed at the location of the gear box, leaving the rear axle and suspension system unchanged.
89 Battery packs can be installed in the volume where engine and fuel tank used to be located. In cases
90 where these volumes are insufficient or too oddly shaped, batteries can also be installed by mounting some
91 seats on a raised platform and installing the batteries underneath. Battery packs on the rooftop could be
92 an alternative solution, even though this raises the center of gravity of the bus significantly (a standard
93 city bus has a maximum weight of about 20 t and needs about 2 t of battery pack, e. g., [40]). A catenary
94 system could be installed for buses in cities with existing trolleybus lines to allow line-charging during
95 operation, which reduces the required size of the battery (and thus the main driver of environmental
96 impacts). Alternatively, a pantograph for point charging may be installed for the same purpose.

97 A pre-fabricated wire tree needs to be installed connecting motors, batteries, and auxiliaries with the
98 existing electric system of the bus (e. g., lights, indicators, displays, air conditioning). Where not yet
99 electrified already, auxiliary motors have to be installed for powering hydraulic systems (e. g., steering),
100 pneumatic systems (e. g., brakes, suspension), and air conditioning. Hybrid buses can be easier to retrofit,
101 because parts of their drive-trains are already electric. As hybrid buses are only about 3% of the European
102 bus fleet, the specifics for retrofitting hybrid buses are neglected here for simplicity.

103 Bus models are highly standardized and each model is available in comparatively large numbers.
104 Therefore, retrofitting can become standardized and partly automated. First small-scale examples are
105 reported to take about one work week for e-retrofitting a single bus [41]. Up-scaling this practice to entire
106 bus fleets may allow to significantly reduce retrofitting time. Also, works could be carried out in standard
107 bus workshops needing little additional equipment, machinery, and skills. Therefore, retrofitting may take
108 each bus off the road for insignificantly longer than regular maintenance, allowing continuous operations
109 of the bus fleet.

110 Assuming a bus retrofit would take one week for 10 workers, each worker can convert four buses a year.
111 In 2022, there were 1.413 million people employed in car maintenance and repair services in EU [42]. As the
112 shift to electric vehicles and public transport will require less repair and maintenance of private cars [43],
113 parts of this skilled workforce could retrofit buses. If 5% of current car mechanics—i. e., 70 000—would
114 work on bus retrofitting, the entire stock of diesel buses in Europe could be retrofitted in just 2.6 years.
115 And afterwards the same people can retrofits trucks and other vehicles, which are on the road in much
116 higher numbers today. Additionally, it would offer an opportunity for suppliers of the automobile industry
117 to innovate retrofit kits and components as a growing new market.

118 Producing a new battery electric bus today causes about 50% more CO_{2,e} emissions than a diesel

Figure 1: Life cycle contribution analysis for the production of a diesel, battery-electric (BEV), and e-retrofit standard city bus for six environmental impact categories from the Environmental Footprint EF3.0 method (Global warming potential 100 years (GWP), abiotic depletion potential (mineral depletion), land use, cumulative energy demand (CED), particulate matter formation impact on human health (PM), and water use), relative to the total impact of the diesel bus.

version ([11], Fig. 1). The additional impacts come mainly from the production of the battery. A retrofit saves impacts from producing the bus frame and body, compensating parts of the increased impacts of the electric drive-train. The greenhouse gas emissions for the retrofit are 20 % lower than a new diesel bus and half that of a new BEV bus, saving 58 t of CO_{2,e} emissions per retrofit compared to a new BEV bus. Additionally, about 1/3 of mineral depletion, cumulative energy demand, particulate matter emissions, and water can be saved.

From a life cycle perspective, the remaining lifetime of retrofitted buses would need to be at least 2/3 that of a new BEV bus to remain environmentally preferable across indicators. Drive-train and suspension typically limit the technical lifetime of any vehicle. When adding a new electric drive-train, the remaining technical lifetime of a retrofitted bus can be assumed close to that for a new BEV bus. In the past decades, the main driver for bus replacements was the need to upgrade emission standards (e. g., EURO 5 to 6) and fuel efficiency. Used buses from Western Europe have often been sold to other countries, where they stay on the road for much longer. For clean electric buses there may be less reason to replace prematurely, as there are neither tailpipe emissions nor engine noise. Furthermore, capital expenditure for BEV buses is significantly higher than for diesel buses, while operating costs are lower [37, 44, 45]. Consequently, there is less economic incentive to frequently upgrade bus models. Evidence is emerging that the lifetime of EV batteries is substantially longer than previously thought [46] and can outlast fossil vehicles [47, 48], making it even more likely that both retrofitted and new BEV buses would last longer than current ones.

4 Bus fleet dynamics

Over the past 25 years, new bus registrations had been roughly constant, averaging 40 000 units per year in EU+4. Bus stocks have slightly increased from about 735 000 units in 2011 to 790 000 units in 2023 (see Section S3 in SM). Consequently, the European bus fleet is currently near a steady state: new registrations replace retirements, but the total number of buses stays about constant. The shift towards battery electric buses started in 2018 and since then reached about 20 % of all new registrations in 2024.

If bus electrification would follow the ambitious stated policy in the EU to ban diesel engines in new cars and light duty vehicles by 2035 [49], the share of new BEV buses would need to reach 100 % in 10 years. Considering a constant bus fleet, the same lifetime distribution for diesel and BEV buses, and a S-shaped adoption of new BEV until 2035 (Fig. 2), electrification of Europe’s bus fleet would be achieved not before 2057. Any delay in BEV adoption, exemptions and extensions to new diesel bus sales would further delay the phase out of diesel emissions. For example, if the last new diesel bus would get sold in

Figure 2: Dynamic fleet development for the scenario with constant fleet and replacements with BEV buses (top row) or including retrofits of buses produced after 2010 (bottom row). Left column shows new bus registrations and retrofits; middle column shows stock of buses on the road; right column shows retirements of buses. Diesel buses are shown in gray, battery electric buses (BEV) in orange and retrofits in green. The fleet of diesel buses produced before 2000 are shown in dark gray, and produced after 2010 in light gray.

149 2050, it would take at least until 2075 to electrify the entire bus fleet. As in 2050 Europe aims to be net
 150 zero, these electrification scenarios clearly are too slow.

151 Retrofitting 95 % of all diesel buses built after 2010 (which is about 60 % of all diesel buses currently
 152 on European roads) allows to phase out diesel buses 15 years earlier (Fig. 2). This can be achieved by
 153 retrofitting a maximum number of 75 000 buses per year over a five-year period, which would employ about
 154 1% of car mechanics currently working on car maintenance and repair. Retrofit ramp-up continues until
 155 2035, when a maximum of 10 % of the bus fleet would be retrofitted in this year. BEV bus production
 156 needs to be scaled one decade later, giving industry more time to build up the required capacity, skills, and
 157 facilities. A comparable outcome can only be achieved through replacements if (i) new bus registrations are
 158 100 % BEV from 2028 onward, (ii) old diesel buses retire early, and (iii) new bus production temporarily
 159 increases by 30 % between 2030 and 2040 (Fig. S2). Retrofitting thus allows to accelerate electrification
 160 without scraping buses prematurely. The older buses are considered for retrofitting, the earlier full
 161 electrification can be achieved. For example, if 95 % of diesel buses produced after 2005 and still on the
 162 road in 2025 would be retrofitted, this would accelerate electrification by another two years.

163 For expanding the bus fleet to scale and strengthen public mobility, either production numbers of new
 164 buses need to increase (Fig. 3) or lifetimes have to be extended (Fig. S3). Keeping diesel buses longer in
 165 operation contradicts emission reduction targets for bus fleets. However, overall emissions in the entire
 166 transport sector would still be lower, if the extended diesel bus operations (approx. 130 g/pkm [30]) would
 167 replace private diesel or gasoline car use (approx. 190 g/pkm [30]). Yet, diesel buses are generally not
 168 perceived as “clean”, and contribute to noise and particulate matter pollution in cities.

169 When including retrofitting, doubling the bus stock on the road can be achieved faster with the same
 170 production output for new buses (Fig. 3), which allows to increase public transport services by 5 % in
 171 the period from 2025 to 2100. Electrification of the bus fleet can again be achieved 15 years earlier.
 172 Bus retirements are delayed in this scenario as retrofitted buses stay longer on the road. Extending the
 173 lifetime of both retrofitted and new electric buses allows to reduce the required production numbers as
 174 well as waste generation. Regardless whether the bus fleet stays constant or is expanded, retrofitting has

Figure 3: Dynamic fleet development for the scenario with doubling stock and replacements with BEV buses (top row) and including retrofits of buses produced after 2010 (bottom row). Left column shows new bus registrations and retrofits; middle column shows stock of buses on the road; right column shows retirements of buses.

175 a consistent effect on the electrification timeline, reaching the threshold of 95 % electrification 15 years
 176 earlier (Fig. S3).

177 5 Reducing impacts and costs

178 The accelerating effect of retrofitting leads to a reduction of cumulative CO_{2,e} emissions until 2100 by
 179 about 300 Mt consistently across comparative scenarios with and without bus retrofits (Fig. S1). The
 180 majority of this 25 % reduction in cumulative emissions from bus fleet operation between 2025 and 2100
 181 comes from accelerating diesel buses phase out, which reduces the emission intensity of passenger transport
 182 with buses significantly earlier (Fig. 4). Cumulative emission savings from retrofitting Europe's bus fleet is
 183 comparable to the emissions of Spain in 2023 [50], not counting the potential emission savings induced by
 184 a shift towards public transport.

185 Retrofitting not only saves environmental impacts, but also overall costs. Currently, evidence is sparse
 186 on the cost of retrofit as for now no large scale retrofit program is in operation. Estimates from pilot
 187 projects suggest, that the cost of a retrofit is up to 1/2 of the cost of a new BEV bus [41]. Economies of scale
 188 would likely reduce the cost of retrofits once work processes are optimized and components standardized.
 189 Assuming conservatively that the cost of retrofit would be 1/2 of the costs for a new BEV bus, retrofitting
 190 could allow to save around 2 % of total costs of bus transport from 2000 to 2100 consistently across
 191 scenarios.

192 6 Discussion and Conclusion

193 This exploratory modeling suggests that retrofitting diesel buses could become a quadruple-win strategy:
 194 it reduces environmental impacts from earlier diesel phase out, saves costs for bus operators, gives the bus
 195 industry more time to ramp BEV bus production, and employs some of the workforce currently working
 196 in automotive maintenance and repairs. Increasing numbers of start-ups and companies offering e-retrofits
 197 indicates growing interest from industry. This paper highlights that it can have a significant systemic

Figure 4: Evolution of emission intensity per passenger-kilometer traveled. Scenarios with replacements through new electric buses in orange, and retrofit as intermediate, circular strategy in green. Lines are plotted for three scenario variants each: replacement, doubling, and life time extension (weak to strong color).

198 benefit, which makes it relevant to develop policy support as well as drive innovations and engineering
 199 optimizations for retrofits to enable scaling.

200 How and if these potential benefits can be realized depends on several factors, such as actual remaining
 201 lifetime of retrofits, training of workforce, organization of workflows, roll-out of charging infrastructure, or
 202 development of costs and economics of retrofits compared to new BEV buses, particularly considering
 203 learning effects. Much can be influenced by engineering design of retrofit components, conversion kits and
 204 workflows. The high standardization and comparatively low variations of bus designs make it possible
 205 to design standardized and semi-automated retrofits optimized for speed. Aiming at high-throughput
 206 retrofit workflows will allow the transformation of the bus fleet with minimal impact on operations. Such
 207 designs should ideally be applicable across bus models currently on the road, as faster electrification can
 208 be achieved with higher shares of the existing bus fleet retrofitted.

209 The remaining lifetime of retrofitted buses is uncertain as there is limited experience with retrofitted
 210 vehicles today. Testing the influence of remaining lifetime of retrofits on the model reveals that it has
 211 little effect on cumulative $\text{CO}_{2,e}$ emissions, yet considerably influence on other impact categories. This
 212 is because $\text{CO}_{2,e}$ emissions are mainly driven by the avoided diesel bus driving emissions, while for
 213 other impact categories production of batteries is the main driver. Shorter remaining lifetime of retrofits
 214 means that more batteries are required in the system, which increases related environmental impacts.
 215 Extending the retrofit lifetime is therefore crucial to reduce overall environmental burdens and material
 216 demand. Research and engineering should therefore aim at designing retrofit strategies that enable lifetime
 217 extensions. But even if retrofit lifetimes fall short of new BEV buses, batteries may be used for different
 218 applications, such as ferries (where weight matters less) or stationary grid storage. The system-wide
 219 implications would need investigation with an expanded system model.

220 Future studies will have to investigate the retrofitting strategy in local contexts within and beyond
 221 Europe, analyze impacts on operations, as well as dive deeper into the technical design of the retrofit
 222 cases. E-retrofit as a strategy may also be expanded to trucks, which are on the road in larger numbers
 223 and a significant challenge for defossilization. To what extent it will be possible and beneficial to also
 224 retrofit passenger cars remains an open question, as cars have a much larger variety in different models,
 225 less space in the engine compartment to fit electric drive-train components, and ownership is distributed.

226 In conclusion, e-retrofit of buses can accelerate the electrification and expansion of bus fleets, while
 227 reducing costs, raw material demand, and environmental impacts. Policy strategies should therefore
 228 consider encouraging the implementation of e-retrofitting as a key circular approach to building a clean,
 229 affordable, and inclusive mobility system for the future.

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Supplementary materials to “E-retrofitting can accelerate Europe’s bus fleet electrification by 15 years”

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236 S1 Extended results

Figure S1: Direct comparison of scenarios without (light color) and with retrofits (dark color): Replacement of existing diesel buses with electric ones at constant stock levels (blue), doubling bus stocks (purple); and doubling bus stocks with lifetime extension of new buses (orange). The scenarios do not include emission savings from replacing private car use, but only direct emissions associated with building, maintaining, and operating Europe’s bus fleet.

Figure S2: Dynamic fleet development for scenarios with constant bus stock and replacements with new BEV buses. Top rows shows a scenario when replacing diesel buses at end of life, while on the bottom row shows the accelerated retirement of diesel buses as well as early phase out of new diesel buses until 2028. Left column shows new bus registrations and retrofits; middle column shows stock of buses on the road; right column shows retirements of buses in million units.

Figure S3: Dynamic fleet development for the scenarios with doubling stock and increased lifetime of new BEV buses and retrofits. Replacements with new BEV buses (top row) and including retrofits of buses produced after 2010 (bottom row). Left column shows new bus registrations and retrofits; middle column shows stock of buses on the road; right column shows retirements of buses.

237 S2 Examples of e-retrofits

238 There are many examples of companies and initiatives e-retrofitting buses and trucks globally. Here is a
 239 short list of examples, which is neither complete nor representative, but rather illustrative of the industry
 240 evolving in this direction.

- 241 • **Trova**, converting trucks to electric trucks in Belgium: <https://www.trovatrucks.eu/>
- 242 • Mine truck conversion in Australia: <https://epca.net.au/>
- 243 • **Neo Truck**: conversion of old Renault trucks in France for use away from roads <https://www.neotrucks.fr/en/>
- 244
- 245 • **DesignWerk** conversion of trucks in Switzerland <https://www.designwerk.com/elektrische-lastkraftwagen/>
- 246
- 247 • **Orten electric** retrofitting of used and new trucks; <https://www.electric-trucks.de/de/umruestung/transporter.html>
- 248
- 249 • **Car solaire**: e-retrofit of mini-buses in Senegal, which are also of cultural value due to their creative
 250 painting. <https://car-solaire.org/>
- 251 • **Kleanbus** in the UK <https://kleanbus.com/>
- 252 • **To Zero** in Germany <https://to-zero.de/en/>
- 253 • **Phoenix Energy** in Nigeria <http://www.phoenixrenewableenergy.com/> make e-retrofits of
 254 tricycles and minibuses https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zy_aluvpaqU as well as develops an
 255 own solar minibus <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JbjgX8BUa5s>
- 256 • **Greenmot** in France <https://www.greenmot.com/en/urban-bus-retrofitting/> originally
 257 developing vehicle test benches, they also make urban bus retrofitting with e-axles
- 258 • **Phoenix Mobility** in France <https://tolv-systems.com/en/> retrofit Renault delivery vans and
 259 mini-trucks to electric
- 260 • **REBOOT** project in the UK, financed by Horizon 2020 of EC, “Retrofit all-Electric Bus for
 261 reduced Operator Operating costs in urban Transport (REBOOT)” run in 2014-2015 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/651630> and was a feasibility study
- 262
- 263 • **reduce-recycle-reuse-eMobility - retrofitting kits for buses** project in Germany, the Nether-
 264 lands and Poland, financed by Horizon 2020 of EC, run in 2015 [https://cordis.europa.eu/pro](https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/673330)
 265 [ject/id/673330](https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/673330) and was a feasibility study.
- 266 • **Tassima** in Germany focuses on e-retrofits of city tour buses, but also wants to expand to normal
 267 city buses, using hub motor wheel axles from Ziehl-Abegg. Seems no longer in operation. <https://www.urban-transport-magazine.com/en/retrofitting-instead-of-new-built-conversion-from-diesel-to-electric-buses/>
- 268
- 269
- 270 • **e-troFit** in Germany: develops e-conversion kits for city buses; uses ZF electric axles with 125 kW
 271 liquid cooled asynchronous motor, 240 kWh battery pack (installed where diesel engines used to be),
 272 which offers a range of 200 km to 250 km. <https://www.peppermotion.com/produkte-loesungen/umruestung-bus/>; and e-retrofit of small and medium trucks <https://www.peppermotion.com/en/products-solutions/repowering-truck/>
- 273
- 274
- 275 • **I SEE electric busses**, a German company converting trucks and buses. A standard diesel bus,
 276 they can convert within 1 work week. The etrofitted buses are supposed to need less than 1 kWh/km.
 277 Costs for the e-trofit were between 300 000 and 350 000 EUR in 2019, which is half the price of a
 278 new electric bus. There is no website to be found, perhaps the company does not exist anymore.
 279 <https://www.urban-transport-magazine.com/en/retrofitting-instead-of-new-built-conversion-from-diesel-to-electric-buses/>, sister company **I SEE electric truck** converting
 280 Opel delivery vans and small trucks into electric. <https://www.i-see.plus/de/index.php>
- 281

- 282 • Bus conversion in Turkey: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3EePKzSdaw8>
- 283 • Bus e-retrofit kits for around 10 000 USD (without battery) on Alibaba: https://www.alibaba.com/product-detail/Brogen-electric-drivetrain-ev-car-motor_1600503360027.html?spm=a2700.7724857.0.0.5da64539UgWUkX

286 S3 Data

287 S3.1 Bus registrations and stocks

288 Statistical data on buses in Europe are collected from ACEA, the European automobile manufacturers' association². ACEA reports new bus registration data regularly since 2007. Data on bus stock is reported
 289 less frequently in periodic "vehicles in use" reports³ and was available for the time period from 2011 till
 290 2023. These time series reveal that total stocks and new registrations are more or less constant for the
 291 entire period in all of Europe (i.e. EU member states + EFTA + UK = EU+4), it can be assumed
 292 that stocks are also at similar values before 2011. This assumption is validated by the fact that bus
 293 transport statistics for EU27 countries (i.e. the transport service provided in passenger kilometers) is
 294 also almost constant for the period 2000 till 2019, with a strong decline due to COIVD-19 and recovery
 295 thereafter⁴. Pre-covid, the average transport performance per bus was 676 000 pkm/bus-a, and with an
 296 average occupancy rate of 10 passengers per bus [30] the average annual driving distance per bus is about
 297 67 600 km/a. This allows to estimate the bus stock for the years 2000-2010.

298 Emissions from bus transport are not directly reported. They can be calculated by multiplying
 299 transport activity with emission factors per passenger kilometers. As almost all buses on the road today
 300 are diesel, bus driving emissions can be estimated with passenger transport emissions from diesel city
 301 buses of around 140 g/pkm in CO_{2,e} [30].

302 Bus retirements (i. e., outflows from Europe and end-of-life (EoL)) are not reported but can be calculated
 303 for the historic period from inflows and stock change.

$$304 \dot{B}_{\text{out}} = \dot{B}_{\text{new}} - \Delta B \quad (1)$$

305 The inflow for the time period from 2000 till 2006 (i. e., where no data is available from ACEA on new
 306 registrations) is set constant with the average inflow from 2007 till 2024.

307 ACEA also provides statistics on the distribution of drive-train types among all newly registered buses
 308 from 2018 till 2024⁵. There is no information provided on the drive train types of the stock. Diesel drive
 309 trains still dominate new registrations by far. Battery-electric is increasing its share from 1 % in 2018 to
 310 20 % in 2024 of all new registrations. Hybrid buses are also increasing in share until 2023 but will also
 311 have to be replaced for a fully decarbonized mobility system. Trolley-buses are not reported as a separate
 312 category but are included in "others" that include gas and hydrogen buses as well. As the total number in
 313 this category is small in comparison to diesel bus registrations, it is assumed for simplicity, that all buses,
 314 which are not BEV, will have to be replaced with electric drive trains. This to-be-replaced category of
 315 buses is called "diesel" after its dominant drive train name-giver. Because new bus registrations in 2018
 316 are 99 % diesel and other fossil drive trains, it is assumed that the initial stock of buses is 100 % diesel in
 317 2000 and all new registrations until 2017 are also diesel.

318 Bus production numbers in Europe are smaller than new registrations at about 28 000 units per year
 319 in 2023⁶. Therefore, Europe is currently net-import reliant on new buses.

320 S3.2 Bus types

321 Local and city buses are dominating in numbers over long distance coaches. According to a survey among
 322 public transport operators from all over the world (but mostly from Europe), the most used bus type is a

²<https://www.acea.auto/cv-registrations/new-commercial-vehicle-registrations-vans-8-3-trucks-6-3-buses-9-2-in-2024/> and preceding press releases back to 2007

³<https://www.acea.auto/publication/report-vehicles-on-european-roads-2025/> back to <https://www.acea.auto/publication/report-vehicles-in-use-europe-2017/>

⁴<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/sustainability-of-europes-mobility-systems/passenger-transport-activity>

⁵<https://www.acea.auto/fuel-cv/fuel-types-of-new-buses-diesel-85-hybrid-4-8-electric-4-alternative-fuels-6-2-share-in-2019-2/>

⁶<https://www.acea.auto/figure/eu-commercial-vehicle-production/>

13 m city bus (68 %), followed by 18 m articulated city buses (12 %) as well as midi (8 %) and mini (5 %) buses [36]⁷. All other bus types (e. g., double-decker, double articulated buses, trolleybuses, coaches, etc.) have a very minor share in the current bus fleet. As some of the non-standard types are larger—and thus requiring more materials and energy—and some are smaller, this justifies the simplification in this study to take an average 13 m city diesel bus as the representative reference.

S3.3 Lifetime estimation

ACEA reports on "vehicles in use" state the average age of the bus fleet for specific years⁸, which is around 12 years. Consequently, average lifetime needs to be about twice as much. Lifetimes of vehicles are commonly modeled as Weibull distributions [15], which is implemented in Insightmaker as a 5th order delay providing a very similar shape of the distribution. The average lifetime is chosen in such a way that vehicle stocks stay constant at the initial value in a steady-state model run without any interventions, and turns out to be 20 years.

Buses used to be replaced in the past 20 years mainly because of tightening noise and particulate matter emission standards. Buses rarely reached their technical end-of-life in most European countries. Electric buses are already much quieter and emission-free, thus it can be expected that they would be operated until they reach technical end-of-life. To test the effect of this possibility, two scenarios are applied: one with standard average lifetimes observed in the historic period (i. e., 20 years) and one with an extended average lifetime for new BEV buses (i. e., 30 years).

The remaining lifetime of retrofits is estimated with an average of 15 years in the standard lifetime scenario, as the average age of diesel buses for retrofit is about 5 years. In the extended lifetime scenario, retrofits are assumed to have the same average lifetime as new BEV buses (i. e., 30 years), as the electric drive-train components are assumed to be the limiting factor for the lifetime of the entire bus.

S3.4 Carbon intensity of electricity

In Europe, the average carbon intensity was declining almost linearly from 385 g/kWh in 2007 to 210 g/kWh in 2023 (ref⁹). From then on, carbon intensity is modeled to decline to zero in 2050 following the stated policy scenario of reaching net zero in 2050 in Europe. Production emissions for new and retrofitted buses are modeled to follow the same trend for all energy-related emissions. Emissions related to material production processes (e.g. steel-making) are assumed constant.

S4 LCA

The standard 13 m city bus is taken as a reference, as it is the dominant bus type on the roads worldwide (68 %). Articulated buses, coaches, and double-decker buses are larger and heavier than standard city buses, yet they are similarly numbered than mini and midi buses, which are smaller and lighter than standard buses.

Using life cycle assessment with inventory data of existing buses based on *calculator bus* [11] with ecoinvent v3.9.1 as background database comparing the following two bus types:

- bus, diesel, 13m-city
- bus, battery electric - overnight charging, 13m-city

To model the retrofit inventory, the BEV bus inventory is modified by only considering those components, which have to be added to the diesel bus.

- driving motor
- battery
- auxiliary drives, power electronics, inverter, converter

⁷https://cms.uitp.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Statistics-Brief_Global-bus-survey-003.pdf

⁸<https://www.acea.auto/publication/report-vehicles-in-use-europe-2023/> and <https://www.acea.auto/publication/report-vehicles-on-european-roads-2025/>

⁹<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/greenhouse-gas-emission-intensity-of-1>

Environmental benefits are calculated based on the comparison of replacing the entire EU+4 diesel bus fleet with new BEV vehicles (replacement scenario) and the considered e-retrofitting scenarios. Investigated impact categories are:

- EF v3.0 EN15804, climate change, global warming potential (GWP100)
- Cumulative Energy Demand, electricity (CED_el), total, energy resources, total
- EF v3.0 EN15804, material resources: metals/minerals, abiotic depletion potential (ADP): elements (ultimate reserves)
- EF v3.0 EN15804, particulate matter formation, impact on human health
- EF v3.0 EN15804, land use, soil quality index
- EF v3.0 EN15804, water use, user deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)

The overall environmental impact savings depend on the point in time, when the diesel bus is replaced with a new BEV bus or retrofitted. Comparing the retrofit option in a standard, static life cycle assessment yields a savings potential in CO_{2,e} emissions of 560 t per diesel bus that is retrofitted after 10 years. In the replacement scenario, a diesel bus is used until the end of its 20 year service life and then replaced with a new BEV bus. In the retrofit scenario, a diesel bus is retrofitted after an initial service of 10 years. The retrofitted bus serves then for another 15 years before being replaced with a new BEV bus. The remaining service life of the BEV bus is subtracted so that the analysis remains within the same time frame of 40 years (see Fig. S4). As the battery and electric drive train are expected to be the main limiting elements for the lifetime of a BEV bus, the retrofit scenario with longer lifetime assumes the same lifetime of the retrofitted bus than a new BEV bus. Note that retrofitting induces an increase in some impact categories: mineral depletion and water use are significantly larger in the retrofit case than in the replacement case. This is because electrification happens 10 years earlier, requiring more batteries in the same time frame.

Figure S4: Life cycle analysis scenario setup (left) and results (right) relative to the replacement scenario. Bus icon adapted from www.flaticon.com

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